

Foraging and Feeding Behaviour Of Indian Peafowl (*Pavo Cristatus*) In Wild Conditions Near Human Habitations

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Abstract

The present study was carried out to evaluate the foraging and feeding behaviour of Indian peafowl (*Pavo cristatus*) in wild conditions at two locations in Neemkathana district of Rajasthan. The Indian Peafowl is a ground dweller, omnivorous, polygamous and large sized beautiful bird. It was found in the study that the peafowl spend a lot of time in foraging. They forage in early morning and in evening and they roost during middle of the day to avoid scorching heat. During feeding on the ground they are extremely vigilant to protect themselves from predators like dogs and cats. They feed on different types of insects, small reptiles, small mammals, caterpillars, seeds, fruits and different vegetation, crops including young shoots of plants. As the diversity of animals is decreasing over the years due various reasons, the same is happening with the population of peafowl. Taking into account the above facts and decrease in number of peafowl, present study was designed to investigate about the foraging and feeding behaviour of peafowl.

Keywords

Peafowl, Omnivorous, Polygamous, Foraging, Vigilant.

Introduction

The Indian peafowl or blue peafowl included in family phasianidae and order Galliformes. It belongs to Indian subcontinent. Male peafowl are called peacock while female peafowls are known as peahens. Although colloquially both are often referred to as peacock. Scientifically it is known as *Pavo cristatus*. Its habitat includes mostly semi arid conditions. It is declared as National bird of India by the Indian Government in 1963. It is included in schedule I of wildlife (protection) Act, 1972 and listed in the threatened category of IUCN Red list. It is beautifully depicted as paintings in temple, art, fables and many mythological books. In Hindu mythology peacock's feathers are used in many rituals. Peacock has vibrant iridescent blue and green beautiful plumage. They spread their plumage to entice the peahens for mating.

Aim of study

Present study was conducted to first know about foraging and feeding behaviour of peafowl at the selected locations in Neemkathana district of Rajasthan.

Review of Literature

Peafowl are omnivorous (eating both plants and animals). These are found in the forest and in villages around human settlement, where water and food is available. Their diet include different varieties of grains like wheat, millet, corn, pumpkin, sunflower seeds, fruits, vegetables, small insects, small mammals and reptiles. Hari Krishnan *et al* (2010) also revealed varieties of food habits in peafowl. Peafowl are diurnal i.e. they sleep during night and active during day. They forage for the food in the day time. Urbanization is increasing in Neemkathana which, in near future may have adverse effect on foraging pattern of peafowl. Changes in foraging pattern would ultimately have negative impact on their number.

Main Text

Study area

Present investigation was carried out at Chhoti jamat (location one) and Guman singh ki dhani (location two) in Neemkathana district of Rajasthan. It is situated at coordinates

27.735018⁰ N and 75.779730⁰ E (Wikipedia). The chosen area is moderately populated and peafowl are easily adapted to live with humans.

Methodology

The peafowl were directly observed by standing at a particular point and by roaming around at both the locations in their natural habitat for two hours each day in the morning and in evening during the month of August in 2023. Conversation was also made with local people to have more information about the bird. As the bird was sighted it was tried to quickly follow it. All the observations were noted in a field note book and later on compiled and concluded at the end of study. Peafowl were not harmed and disturbed during the study.

Result and Discussion

Indian peafowl are ground foragers. In the present study it was noted that they spend a lot of time in foraging. They prefer to forage early in morning and in the late afternoon while they avoid hot sun during middle of the day. They fly up to the trees to roost during the middle of the day to stay away from the blazing sun. It was often observed that peahens forage in groups (Photo 1 a & b) while peacock forages alone or with peahens (Photo 2 a & b). It shows peacock's polygamous nature too (Photo 5 b). They keep themselves extremely vigilant while feeding on the ground (Photo 3 a & b). As they feel any kind of bustle they rapidly fly to the trees or roof of houses or any other top structures. In the present study photo (3 a) showing that dog is approaching to peacock, it quickly flew up to the wall. Hence by their vigilant nature they avoid predation and maximize their fitness while foraging. (Photo 3 b). Beauchamp 2009 and Yorzinski (2015) also found that quick vigilant behaviour enhanced the protection of *Gallus gallus*.

The diet of peafowl constituted both animal matter and vegetable matter. They feed on termite in decaying logs. Among animals they feed on insects, white grub, snails, slugs, aphids, mealy bugs, small reptiles etc. Animal matter is rich source of protein for them. Charlton *et al*, 2015 and Nowak *et al*, 2016 found that insects are good source of protein and plants provide rich calcium which is required for egg production. They also forage on dung heap as they find many insects and caterpillars in dung heap, which they love to feed upon. (Photo 4 a & b). Among plants they feed on young shoots of small vegetation, herbs, flower buds, petals, leaves and grass. Yasmin and Yahya also observed that peafowl fed on seeds, leaves and herbs. They also like to eat grains of wheat, Bajra, Rice, Corn, Sorghum which were provided to them throughout the year by local people residing at the chosen locations. Some people also offer them lentil, maize and sesame. Sathyanarayana *et al*, 2005 also recorded that peafowl fed on grains.

1 (a)

1 (b)

Photo 1 (a) and (b) Peahens foraging in groups

2 (a)

2(b)

Photo 2 (a) and (b) Peacock foraging alone

3 (a)

3 (b)

Photo 3. As the dog is approaching peacock flew up to wall.